

The Importance of Pedagogical Skills in Organizing the Educational Process in Higher Education

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Abstract: The author of the article reveals the essence of teaching art, which expresses a high level of educational activities, special pedagogical skill, based on the relationship and interdependence of theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as the teacher's personality, his creative experience, social and professional views.

Keywords: teaching art; design skills; communication skills.

Introduction: The highest level of pedagogical activity, manifested in the constant improvement of the art of teaching, education and development of a person, is pedagogical mastery. The pedagogical mastery of a higher education teacher is expressed in his professional activity and does not exist separately from the personality. In pedagogy, there is no single view on the essence of the professional mastery of a teacher. Thus, some scientists associate mastery with mastering the methods and techniques of education, others - with the personality of the teacher, his individuality. The components of pedagogical mastery are the humanistic focus of the teacher's activity, professional knowledge, pedagogical abilities and pedagogical technique.

Creative abilities occupy a special place in the structure of pedagogical mastery. The term "creativity" is used to denote the ability that reflects the property of an individual to create new concepts and develop new skills. There are two types of creativity: potential and actual. Potential creativity is considered as a potential predisposition, expressed in the form of basic readiness to acquire actual creativity in certain external conditions, to manifest creative activity. Creativity is associated with the creative achievements of the individual. Here it is worth paying attention to the pedagogical creativity of the individual. It has a unique character, takes place in an atmosphere of direct interaction with students, requires the teacher to constantly manage their mental states and creative well-being. Several levels of pedagogical creativity are distinguished.

In modern conditions, a creative teacher is, first of all, a researcher with scientific psychological and pedagogical thinking, a high level of pedagogical skills, developed pedagogical intuition, critical analysis, and a need for professional self-development. The specificity of pedagogical creativity at a university is that it should be considered as co-creation of a teacher and students. The teacher's readiness to take the student's position, in the student's position, or in opposition to him is an important condition for co-creation. This attitude is opposite to the orientation of higher education on the so-called affirmative nature: a question posed in a lecture or at a seminar must certainly be resolved, and resolved unambiguously, once and for all. The teacher's complicit attitude is to recognize

the student's right to an incorrect answer, a mistake, and also to allow him to express his point of view based on his own experience. In addition, it is necessary to take into account that the student's answers that are inadequate to the question posed are the result of a misunderstanding of the question or an incorrect formulation of it by the teacher. The internal subjective side of pedagogical mastery includes knowledge, abilities, skills, value orientations and priorities, general and professional culture, professionally important personal qualities, attitude to pedagogical activity, pedagogical abilities, character traits adequate to the requirements of the profession, manifestations of temperament, features of mental processes. Pedagogical mastery, therefore, can be defined as a set of personal properties that ensure a high level of self-organization of professional activity. The most important condition for the development of a teacher's mastery is the definition of an individual style of his pedagogical activity. Style is a stable system of tasks, methods and tactics of activity, conditioned by the natural characteristics of a person, ensuring the effectiveness of his work.

Literature Analysis: Knowledge of didactics and its creative application largely direct the formation of pedagogical skills of a higher education teacher. Historically, there are different opinions regarding the role of didactics in the activities of a secondary and higher education teacher. Some believe that didactics should arm a teacher with specific recommendations for constructing the educational process. Others believe that didactics fetters the creative independence of a teacher, since everything depends on the depth of his knowledge of the discipline he teaches, on his pedagogical experience. Undoubtedly, a higher education teacher resolves many situations related to the training of future specialists. The components of pedagogical skills, defined in modern pedagogical literature, can be divided into four relatively independent elements:- skill of organizing collective and individual educational activities;

Pedagogical skills of a higher education teacher

- ✓ skill of transmitting knowledge;
- ✓ skill of forming experience of activity;
- ✓ skill of mastering pedagogical technology

All these four components are closely intertwined and mutually reinforce each other. The dominant component, in our opinion, is the skill of the organizer of collective and individual activities. This component is most important for students and the most difficult to implement for a teacher. The ability to combine and fill all goals with specific content, select methods, means and forms is, in our opinion, an indicator of the teacher's skill in organizing collective and individual students' activities. No less important are both the skill of transferring knowledge and the skill of forming the experience of the activity. Both of these components are most closely related to the organizational and methodological goals of the pedagogical process, as well as to the features of the style of individual pedagogical activity of the teacher.

Research Methodology: The structure of pedagogical mastery includes: the ability to see a pedagogical problem, select, adapt and convey didactic material to students, and organize creative educational cooperation based on equal dialogue. The most important pedagogical skills include the ability to understand the internal position and state of the student and, on this basis, individualize the educational process.

The content of the elements of a professional and pedagogical nature of a master teacher should consist of:

- 1) a system of professional and pedagogical knowledge;
- 2) a system of professional and pedagogical skills and abilities;

- 3) experience of creative pedagogical activity;
- 4) formed personal professionally significant qualities of a teacher.

Professional and pedagogical skills and abilities should cover the same components as knowledge, i.e. in the most general form these should be skills and abilities:

- 1) selection, didactic organization and transmission of educational content as an object of activity of students;
- 2) communication with students; use of opportunities for development and education in the learning process, transfer from the level of "object of education, upbringing" to the level of "subject of education, upbringing"; formation in students of experience in carrying out activities and organizing this activity to master the content;
- 3) organization and implementation of the teacher's own activities in the learning process;
- 4) formation of oneself as a person and a teacher, development of professionally significant qualities and pedagogical abilities, professional-pedagogical and social orientation of the individual, orientation-value relations of the individual;
- 5) organization of the pedagogical process: creation of a toolkit of pedagogical influence as a system as a whole with the aim of solving the problems of education, upbringing and development of students in the learning process.

Skills and abilities, being an integral part of the foundations of pedagogical mastery, are so important that some researchers consider the level of skills to be decisive in the mastery of a teacher.

These components, related to the aspects of the teacher's personality, are the basis of the internal model of the teacher's behavior. The personal aspect of the foundations of pedagogical skill is nothing more than the conscious and unconscious pedagogical influence of the teacher's personality on the students, contributing to the achievement of the final goal.

Conclusion. A master of pedagogical work is, first of all, a highly competent specialist in the psychological-pedagogical and subject area, who is able to reproduce professional knowledge, skills and abilities at a high level.

The effectiveness of his pedagogical activity is influenced by such factors as:

- ✓ good knowledge of his subject, which gives the teacher emancipation and confidence during the lesson;
- ✓ the ability to constantly self-study (assimilation of new things in the subject, pedagogical, psychological areas);
- ✓ the presence of a need for achievements (the desire to surpass the already achieved level).

Thus, pedagogical mastery is based on a system of knowledge, skills, abilities, closely related to the professionally important qualities of the teacher, allowing him to carry out his activities at a high level of performance and effectively achieve the goals of education and training of students.

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